

Crystallisation Behaviour of the Tsokar Lake Brine at 75° and 95 – 106° using Puga's Geothermal Energy

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Crystallisation behaviour of Tsokar lake brine at 75° and 95 – 106° has been established utilising Puga's geothermal energy. It has been established that evaporation at 75° is technically and economically feasible. The quantity of heat required to process 12000 litres of brine comes to 7500 compared to 187×10^5 kcal/h available at Puga. The cost of production of technical grade anhydrous sodium sulphate has been calculated. It has also been established that crystallisation route at 75° is similar to D'ans isotherm at 83° for $\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 - \text{K}_2\text{SO}_4 - \text{MgSO}_4 - \text{Na}_2\text{Cl}_2 - \text{K}_2\text{Cl}_2 - \text{H}_2\text{O}$ system except for langbenite (instead leonite is crystallised). The crystallisation starts with thenardite, vanthofite and glaserite followed by leonite sylvite, carnallite and kieserite

INDIA'S most promising geothermal fields lie at Puga, adjacent to Tsokar lake of Ladakh. In Puga at a depth of about 40 – 60 m geothermal fluids (a mixture of saturated steam and hot water) have been struck, having temperature of 110 – 30° and pressure of 2 kg psi. About 50 such geothermal wells have been drilled by GSI and most of them are active. According to a rough estimate, the total flow is of the order of 20 tonnes of steam and 170 tonnes of hot water per hour. This gives total heat content of 187×10^5 kcal/h. Keeping in view the huge deposits of salts and non-availability of conventional energy at Tsokar, an attempt has been made in the present investigation to harness this geothermal energy for extraction of salts from Tsokar lake brine. Earlier, besides solar evaporation¹, crystallisation behaviour of the lake brine at elevated temperature (50°) had been established² which takes 7 days to complete one set of experiment. In this investigation an attempt has been made to study crystallisation behaviour of lake brine at 75° and boiling (95 – 106°), i.e. using direct complete geothermal fluids. Besides, an attempt has also

been made to work out economic feasibility for the extraction of raw salts from brine on large scale at 75°.

Experimental

The lake brine (20 lit ; 21.8° Be' : Found, Cl^- , 6.73 ; Mg^{2+} , 1.31 ; Na^+ , 5.00 ; K^+ , 1.87 ; $\text{B}_4\text{O}_7^{2-}$, 0.52%) in each set was subjected to evaporation at 75° and boiling (95 – 106°) separately in an open stainless steel container. Four salt fractions were collected at 35.7, 36.6, 37.45° Be' and enmass on crystallisation at 75°, and three salt fractions were collected at 37.45, 35.70° Be' and enmass on crystallisation at boiling (95 – 106°). It took four days for completion of one set of experiment at 75° and 27 h for completion of one set of experiment at boiling (95 – 106°). The weight of salts separated with change in density was recorded, alongwith chemical composition of the deposited salts in equilibrium with brine with change in density of the brine (Table 1). The salt fractions were analysed by usual method of analysis³; sulphate by barium chloride method, chloride by silver nitrate method, sodium

TABLE 1 – CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF THE SALT FRACTIONS AT DIFFERENT DENSITIES*

Density γ	°Be'	Salt fraction collected	Na-sulphate %	K-sulphate %	Mg-sulphate %	Na-chloride %	K-chloride %	Mg-chloride %	Na-borate %	Wt. of salt collected kg
1.329	35.7	75C-1	81.96	2.51	5.54	6.13	–	–	0.36	1.100
1.340	36.6	75C-2	50.13	6.12	18.66	19.43	–	–	0.60	2.500
1.350	37.45	75C-3	–	–	20.49	41.42	28.60	1.31	1.21	0.440
–	–	75C-4	–	–	13.61	17.31	25.49	15.21	4.14	0.100
1.360	37.45	GEC-1	37.73	12.25	28.60	14.60	–	–	1.82	2.500
1.330	35.70	GEC-2	28.36	12.92	29.55	16.35	–	–	1.82	1.500
–	–	GEC-3	–	–	10.46	42.89	20.59	5.24	2.85	0.500

*Quantity of brine taken in each set = 20 lit.

TABLE 2—MINERALOGICAL COMPOSITION OF THE SALT FRACTIONS

Salt fraction	Thenerdite %	Vanthofite %	Glaserite %	Langbenite %	Arca-nite %	Halite %	Sylvite %	Carnallite %	Kieserite %	Na-borate penta-hydrate %	Free moisture %	Total
75C-1	55.54	25.15	9.33	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.52	2.93	99.59
75C-2	—	64.29	—	7.75	2.87	19.43	—	—	—	0.86	4.52	99.72
75C-3	—	—	—	—	—	19.75	49.25	3.81	23.55	1.75	1.65	99.76
75C-4	—	—	—	—	—	6.66	24.24	44.36	15.64	6.00	2.66	99.56
GEC-1	—	48.38	—	29.17	—	14.60	—	—	1.18	2.63	3.67	99.63
GEC-2	—	36.37	—	30.77	—	16.35	—	—	4.24	2.63	9.62	99.72
GEC-3	—	—	—	—	—	29.97	29.41	13.74	42.02	4.13	9.68	99.95

and potassium by flame photometer, magnesium by EDTA, and borate by neutralisation. The mineralogical composition of the salts separated were worked out and recorded in Table 2. Differential thermal analysis (DTA) curves of the salt fractions were recorded on a MOM derivatograph (Hungary). The reference material used for DTA was anhydrous reagent grade Al_2O_3 . The thermocouple used was of Pt-Pt-Rh. Salt crops for thermal analysis were ground (just before the thermal analysis) to pass 150 mesh ISS sieve.

Also the brine (600 lit) was subjected to evaporation at 75° in an open crystalliser (stainless steel) and two major salts crops were collected at 36.6° Be' and en mass. The geothermal fluids were supplied to the jacket of the crystalliser through a steam separator. At the start, complete geothermal fluids (containing saturated steam and hot water) were passed through the jacket till brine attained a temperature of 75° and steam was then separated out and only hot water of geothermal fluids was supplied to the jacket of the crystalliser to maintain the temperature of evaporation at 75°.

Results and Discussions

With evaporation of the brine at 75°, sodium sulphate is first to separate out, upto density of 36.6° Be' (75C-2) and the maximum potassium ion separated ($K=1.13, 2.75; 15.00$ and 13.37% in salt fractions 75C-1 to 75C-4) is 2.75 percent. Immediately after 36.6° Be' (75C-2), the potassium ion concentration is 15.00 and 13.37% (in the last two fractions), that is the major portion of potassium salts are separated only after brine achieves density of 36.6° Be'. This is similar to crystallisation behaviour of brine at 50°, while as on evaporation of brine at boiling (95–106°) the crystallisation is brisk, the chemical composition of the salt fractions is almost similar, i.e. there is no major separation of sodium and potassium salts as at 75°. The probable mineralogical composition of the salt fraction (Table 2) shows that thenerdite, vanthofite and glaserite crystallise first followed by langbenite, carnallite and kieserite at 75°, while as with geothermal energy it is vanthofite and langbenite which crystallise first followed by carnallite and kieserite.

In salt fraction 75C-1 (Table 2) vanthofite, thenerdite and glaserite predominates. This is also confirmed by DTA studies. The endothermic effect due to decomposition of vanthofite at 515° is observed at 525°. The endothermic effect due to polymorphic transformation of glaserite at 437°, is observed at 455°, while endothermic effect due to polymorphic transformation of thenerdite at 240° is observed at 265°. Besides the above thermal effects in DTA, there are also endothermic effects at 140° and 580°, which may be attributed to dehydration and polymorphic transformation of leonite formed in this fraction on long standing. The salt fraction 75C-2 has mainly vanthofite and langbenite in it. The endothermic effect due to decomposition of vanthofite at 515° is observed at 535°. Langbenite which shows only one thermal effect at 930° due to melting is not observed in DTA, instead there are endothermic effects at 185° and 620°, which is attributed to dehydration and polymorphic transformation of leonite, which must have been formed on standing. Besides above thermal effects there is endothermic effect at 450°, which is attributed to polymorphic transformation of glassrite, which might have been formed by action of free potassium sulphate with sodium sulphate in the salt fraction.

The salt fraction 75C-3 and 75C-4 have mainly carnallite and kieserite in them. This is also confirmed by DTA studies. The endothermic effect due to boiling of solution at 190° is observed at 195° and 190° in 75C-3 and 75C-4 respectively. The endothermic effect due to melting of carnallite is however overlapped by endotherm at 190°. The endothermic effect due to dehydration of carnallite at 230° is observed at 235° and 240° in 75C-3 and 75C-4 respectively. While endothermic effect due to melting of dehydrated carnallite at 425° is observed at 435° and 430°. The endothermic effect due to polymorphic transformation of kieserite at 340° is observed at 360° in both 75C-3 and 75C-4 salt fractions. In addition to this there is a thermal effect (endotherm) at 615° and 630° in 75C-3 and 75C-4 respectively, which is attributed to polymorphic transformation of leonite formed on standing.

In the salt fraction GEC-1 and GEC-2, the salts comprises chiefly of vanthofite and langbenite. This is also confirmed by DTA studies. There is a well resolved endothermic effect at 520° due to decomposition of vanthofite. But due to forced evaporation, there are free salts of sodium sulphate and magnesium sulphate in these salt fractions, which is revealed by the fact that there is a small typical endotherm of thenerdite at 240° due to its polymorphic transition. There is also a small endothermic effect at 320° which reveals that kieserite is also present in these salt fractions and is not bonded with sodium sulphate completely to form vanthofite. No thermal effect due to lengbenite at 930° is observed but instead the typical endotherm due to polymorphic transition of leonite at 570° and 580° in GEC-1 and GEC-2 respectively is observed. The other two endothermic effects of leonite are not well resolved. The presence of endotherms at 570° and 580° in GEC-1 and GEC-2 reveals that due to forced evaporation, langbenite is not formed completely and is associated with a mixture of potassium sulphate and magnesium sulphate which on standing give rise to leonite in the presence of free moisture available in the salt fractions.

Isotherm at 55°^s and 83°^e (Lowenberz's method) along with solubility data^v have been chosen to predict crystallisation route. The salt phases encountered in isotherm at 55° starts from thenerdite, glaserite, vanthofite, astrakanite, sylvite, leonite, langbenite, loweite, kainite, kieserite, carnallite and ends in bischoffite phase saturated with sodium chloride. In isotherm at 83°, the crystallisation starts from thenerdite, vanthofite, glaserite, loweite, langbenite, sylvite, kieserite, carnallite and ends in bischoffite salt phase, saturated with sodium chloride invariably.

It is evident from Table 2 and DTA that Tsokar lake brine when subjected to evaporation at 75°, separated out thenerdite, vanthofite and glaserite, followed by leonite (and not langbenite), sylvite, carnallite and kieserite. This agrees with the crystallisation route predicted in $\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 - \text{MgSO}_4 - \text{K}_2\text{SO}_4 - \text{Na}_2\text{Cl}_2 - \text{K}_2\text{Cl}_2 - \text{MgCl}_2 - \text{H}_2\text{O}$ system at 83° except for langbenite, instead leonite is present. There are a number of well

defined phases which are surpassed in this system due to forced evaporation.

The mineralogical composition (Table 2) shows high quantities of free moisture. Some of the solid phases which are devoid of water of crystallisation absorb this free moisture to give rise to hydrated solid phases. Thus in salt fraction 75C-2, langbenite absorb free moisture to give rise to leonite, which otherwise does not separate out at 75°. In this study the crystallisation starts from thenerdite, vanthofite and glaserite followed by leonite, sylvite, carnallite and kieserite. On the other hand, the evaporation by geothermal energy is quite brisk and random. It does not have a well defined pattern as in the case of solar evaporation¹. The salts separated are almost a mixture of salts with the result that further processing to get pure individual salts or double salts of industrial utility becomes difficult.

Large scale trials : In 500 litre capacity trial (C), 95900 kg of salts are obtained upto 36 6° Be' density in which major portion is sodium sulphate (Table 3). After 36 6° Be' till complete evaporation, the salts obtained (14.50 kg) are mostly potassium chloride, sodium chloride, magnesium chloride and magnesium sulphate. Taking into consideration 87.87 percent^s recovery of sodium sulphate from raw sodium sulphate of Tsokar lake; out of 95.90 kg of raw sodium sulphate (purity 58.67%) of trial-C, LSC-1, 49.43 kg of pure sodium sulphate is recoverable. Taking into account the recovery of only sodium sulphate from brine at the moment, with geothermal energy, the break-even point of the project comes with processing of 12000 lit of lake brine per day. The cost of production of technical grade anhydrous sodium sulphate comes to Rs. 1970 per tonne. The complete project details have been worked out.

Considering the temperature of the brine at 15° the quantity of heat required for its evaporation at 75° comes to 30000 kcal, i.e. 312.5 kcal/h. Thus the quantity of heat required by 12000 lit of brine comes to 7500 kcal/h, which is much low compared to the heat flow available at Puga (187×10^6 kcal/h).

TABLE 3 - CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF THE SALT CROPS WITH LARGE TRIALS*

Trial no.	Crop no.	Na-sulphate	K-sulphate	Mg-sulphate	Na-chloride	K-chloride	Mg-chloride	Wt. of crop kg
A	LSC-1	60.82	4.30	13.68	17.55	-	-	96.600
	LSC-2	-	-	21.20	31.28	22.86	16.70	14.200
B	LSC-1	60.35	3.96	13.10	18.16	-	-	96.100
	LSC-2	-	-	20.88	30.67	23.45	16.20	14.400
C	LSC-1	58.67	4.01	13.36	17.98	-	-	95.900
	LSC-2	-	-	21.28	30.47	22.01	15.27	14.500

*Quantity of brine taken in each trial = 500 lit.

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